

The Influence of Internal Quality Assurance Guidelines on Teachers' Instructional Effectiveness: A Mixed-Methods Analysis from Public Secondary Schools in Morogoro Region, Tanzania

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Abstract:

The Internal Quality Assurance (IQA) guidelines are essential for effective instructional delivery in educational institutions, serving as a framework that promotes continuous improvement, accountability, and high pedagogical standards within the education system. Guided by Deming's Total Quality Management (TQM) theory, this study examines the Influence of Internal Quality Assurance Guidelines on Teachers' Instructional Effectiveness in Public Secondary Schools in Morogoro Region, Tanzania. Using a convergent mixed-methods approach that combined both quantitative and qualitative methods guided by the pragmatist research philosophy, the study sampled 371 respondents, including 225 teachers, 100 Internal Quality Assurance Team (IQAT) members, 7 Chief District Quality Assurance Officers (CDQAOs), and 7 District Secondary Education Officers (DSEOs) from the 07 districts in the Morogoro region. Questionnaires were given to teachers for quantitative data collection, while structured interviews with CDQAOs and DSEOs, along with Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) with IQATs, gathered qualitative data. Quantitative data were analyzed descriptively using SPSS version 20, and qualitative data were analyzed using thematic analysis procedures. The findings revealed that IQA guidelines implementation enhances teachers' instructional effectiveness, particularly in curriculum monitoring, pedagogical supervision, and assessment practices. However, the study also identified contextual barriers, including inadequate resources, shortage of teaching workforce, and limited teacher training on IQA implementation, which constrain the realization of IQA objectives. The study concludes that strengthening IQA mechanisms is fundamental to improving teaching quality and sustaining educational standards in public secondary schools. The study recommends that the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology (MoEST) institutionalize continuous capacity-building programs on IQA operationalization and strengthen schools' IQATs to sustain IQA practices. The policymakers should integrate a teacher feedback mechanism into the IQA system to foster collective ownership of the quality improvement process, and further research should focus on examining the long-term effects of IQA guidelines implementation on learners' outcomes.

Keywords: Internal Quality Assurance, Instructional Effectiveness, Total Quality Management, Public Secondary Schools

1. INTRODUCTION

Globally, the Internal Quality Assurance (IQA) guidelines in education represent a systematic process through which educational institutions implement, monitor, evaluate, and improve the quality of the teaching and learning process. According to the literature, many countries and schools have developed IQA frameworks that include clearly defined policies, standardized procedures for lesson observation, learner assessment, curriculum implementation, staff performance appraisal, and evidence-based feedback for teachers (Suyanto and Ulfah, 2024). This framework is intended to strengthen

accountability, enhance instructional consistency, and align classroom practices with national curricula and global quality standards, thereby promoting student learning outcomes and instructional effectiveness. According to Yoon and Goddard (2023), instructional effectiveness is defined as the degree to which teaching and learning practices achieve intended learning outcomes.

The evidence indicates that regular classroom observation, structured feedback, peer review, and data-driven reflection integrated in IQA guidelines can enhance teacher motivation, pedagogical strategies, and classroom management practices (Kauko et al., 2022).

However, the findings from the study conducted by Kingu and Wandela (2022) suggest that IQA generates diverse effects depending on how guidelines are designed, implemented, and contextualized, especially when they are perceived as bureaucratic, top-down, and disconnected from teachers' daily activities.

According to Özkan and Şahin (2025), in their international comparative study, they highlight that the impact of IQA guidelines on instructional effectiveness is highly context-dependent, varying across governance models, resource levels, and teachers' support systems. In some settings, IQA guidelines integrated with professional learning communities, mentoring, and continuous professional development, foster a culture of improvement rather than mere compliance. In others, IQA guidelines are perceived as a compliance and surveillance mechanism for teachers and institutional activities, thus undermining autonomy and teacher agency (Ali & Hermansyah, 2024). These interplays highlight a need for more context-specific inquiries on how IQA guidelines are translated into measurable instructional gains across educational institutions.

Across Africa, educational policy has raised concerns about improving the quality of teaching and learning in educational institutions. Access to education has been expanded following educational reforms and commitments to global agendas such as Education for All and the Sustainable Development Goals (ESCAP, 2019). In ensuring that educational standards are maintained, IQA guidelines are increasingly viewed as a vital tool for guiding teaching practices and monitoring of instructional processes across educational institutions. IQA guidelines, which include structured lesson planning, peer supervision, classroom observation, evaluation of teaching materials, and monitoring of assessment practices, are designed to promote accountability, professional collaboration, and continuous improvement among teachers across countries' educational systems (Phumphongkhochasorn et al., 2022). The evidence suggests that when the guidelines are effectively implemented, the IQA mechanism can support teachers in refining pedagogical strategies, aligning instruction with curriculum requirements, and responding to learners' needs

(Arslan, 2025). A study by Quansah (2022) in sub-Saharan Africa further indicated that schools with well-implemented IQA guidelines tend to demonstrate teacher preparedness and more consistent monitoring of the teaching and learning process.

Despite the growing emphasis on IQA across African countries' education systems, the practical influences of the guidelines on teachers' instructional effectiveness remain uneven and insufficiently documented. Evidence indicates that challenges such as inadequate professional training in IQA implementation, weak leadership structures, and insufficient monitoring hinder the effective operationalization of IQA guidelines; as a result, the intended benefits of IQA are not fully realized at the classroom and institutional levels (Asuamah and Antwi, 2024). Therefore, understanding how IQA guidelines shape teachers' instructional effectiveness is crucial for informing policy implementation and strengthening the quality of secondary education across Africa.

The quest for quality education improvement in public secondary education in Tanzania has become a national priority, particularly following the rapid expansion of access to education through policies such as the Secondary Education Development Plan and the implementation of fee-free basic education (URT, 2023). While these initiatives have significantly increased student enrollment, the country's education system has also intensified concerns about the quality of teaching and learning in public secondary schools. In response to that, the government has strengthened institutional mechanisms aimed at monitoring and improving the quality of teaching and learning processes across schools through the adoption of IQA guidelines (URT, 2019). The guidelines are intended to support systematic supervision of teaching activities, promote professional accountability among teachers, and enhance adherence to national curriculum standards. The activities are done through IQA practices, which include lesson plan verification, classroom observation by the SIQATs and the school heads, review of teaching records, and monitoring of students' assessment procedures (URT, 2017). Through these processes, schools are expected to promote reflective teaching practices and ensure that instructional activities

contribute effectively to student academic achievements.

Despite the policy efforts to ensure the presence of IQA guidelines across public secondary schools, the concerns persist regarding their practical effectiveness in improving teachers' instructional practices. The evidence shows that IQA practices are inconsistently implemented and treated as administrative requirements rather than tools for pedagogical improvements across public secondary schools (Ng'hoboko, 2024; Mutemi & Mwila, 2025). As a result, instructional effectiveness characterized by clear lesson preparation, active student engagement, appropriate use of teaching methods, and effective assessment practices remains suboptimal in many schools. However, in the Morogoro region, where public secondary schools face various challenges, including large class sizes, a shortage of teaching and learning resources, and limited teachers' professional development, the practical effectiveness of these guidelines remains poorly documented. While previous studies have documented policy intentions and implementation challenges, there is limited evidence on specific mechanisms through which IQA guidelines shape instructional effectiveness at the school level.

Grounded in TQM theory, which emphasizes continuous improvement, customer focus, and process-oriented management, this study addresses these gaps by examining the Influence of Internal Quality Assurance Guidelines on Teachers' Instructional Effectiveness in public secondary Schools in Morogoro Region, Tanzania, using a mixed-methods approach that combines quantitative analysis of instructional practices and qualitative insights from the SIQATS, DSEOS, and CDQAOs. This approach aims to understand how IQA guidelines enhance instructional effectiveness, while identifying barriers and enablers. Focusing on the Morogoro region provides region-specific evidence that contributes to national educational policy discussions on strengthening IQA systems. The findings offer practical recommendations for enhancing the implementation of IQA guidelines to support more effective teaching practices in Tanzania's public secondary schools.

1.1 Research Question

How do IQA guidelines enhance teachers' instructional effectiveness in PSSs?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The theoretical and empirical were reviewed regarding the theme of the research question. The TQM Theory guided the study.

2.1 Total QMT Theory

Total Quality Management Theory, originally developed in the manufacturing industry by Deming (1986) and Juran (1988), emphasizes continuous improvement, customer satisfaction, and systematic process optimization through employee involvement and data-driven decision-making. In educational settings, TQM has been adopted to promote institutional excellence by treating the teaching and learning process as interconnected systems subjected to ongoing refinement, where IQA mechanisms serve as a tool for monitoring inputs, processes, and outputs (Falah & Firdaus, 2025). The core TQM principles, including leadership commitment, process focus, employee empowerment, and evidence-based evaluation, align closely with the operationalization of IQA guidelines in schools, where they facilitate structured supervision of instructional practices, peer collaboration among teachers, alignment of classroom activities with learners' needs, and curriculum standards. This study applies TQM theory as a theoretical lens to examine how IQA guidelines influence teachers' instructional effectiveness in public secondary schools in the Morogoro region, Tanzania. It is posited that effective TQM implementation can transform IQA from a compliance exercise into a catalyst for pedagogical transformation and sustained instructional improvements.

2.1.2 The Strength of the TQM Theory

The strength of TQM theory lies in its systematic approach to continuous improvement, which integrates leadership commitment, stakeholder participation, and evidence-based processes to achieve organizational excellence (Jester, 2024). In the education context, TQM theory provides a powerful framework for aligning institutional structures, teaching practices, and assessment

systems toward the shared goal of improving learning effectiveness. It emphasizes collective responsibility and proactive problem-solving, encouraging teachers, administrators, and policy makers to collaboratively identify inefficiencies, set quality standards, and evaluate performance using reliable data. This participatory and process-oriented nature of TQM fosters a culture of accountability, professional empowerment, and institutional transformation. By integrating QA within everyday teaching and management practices, TQM enhances instructional effectiveness and sustainability, making it a particularly relevant theoretical foundation for examining how IQA guidelines can transform the educational quality in public secondary schools.

2.1.3 Application of the TQM Theory to the Study

In this study, the TQM theory is applied as the guiding framework to explain how internal quality assurance guidelines enhance teachers' instructional effectiveness in public secondary schools. TQM emphasizes continuous improvement, teamwork, leadership commitment, and a strong focus on quality in every process. When applied to the education context, the "customers" are students, and quality teaching becomes a key product shaped by effective IQA systems. The IQA guidelines, such as lesson supervision, peer review, assessment moderation, and performance evaluations, reflect the process-oriented and improvement-driven nature of TQM. By aligning these practices with TQM principles, schools create a culture of shared responsibility, reflective practice, and data-informed decision-making that continuously improve teaching standards and learning outcomes. Therefore, the application of TQM in this study provides a theoretical basis for understanding how structured IQA guidelines enhance sustainable instructional effectiveness and overall educational excellence in Morogoro region public secondary schools.

2.2 The Review of the Related Empirical Literature

IQA Guidelines on Enhancing Teachers' Instructional Effectiveness in PSSs

The empirical studies on IQA in education increasingly show that well-designed school-based IQA guidelines can enhance teachers' instructional effectiveness; however, they also reveal important contextual variations and implementation challenges that inform the present study. Drawing on Ali and Hermansyah's (2024) comparative analysis of Indonesia and Finland, employing a qualitative case study approach that examined government documents, journals, and reports through an input-process-output framework. Their findings provided valuable insights into the IQA system, revealing notable similarities in teacher qualification standards and curriculum oversight, yet underscored the stark contrasts, particularly Finland's emphasis on early childhood education as a foundation for lifelong learning compared to Indonesia's traditional prioritization of basic and secondary levels. While the study highlighted policy scope without delving into implementation dynamics, it recommended that Indonesia adopt Finland's decentralized supervision and competitive teacher recruitment models to strengthen IQA efficacy. Their work holds particular relevance for the current study in Tanzania public secondary schools as it illustrates how centralized versus developed quality mechanisms influence the instructional system, thereby informing how to enhance teachers' classroom effectiveness in resource-constrained settings of the Morogoro region, Tanzania.

Correspondingly, in sub-Saharan Africa, Idris (2023) conducted a study in Lagos State, Nigeria, to examine the relationship between quality assurance practices and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools. The study revealed that structured QA mechanisms such as teacher training, mentoring, and continuous professional development significantly enhance instructional delivery, classroom management, and job satisfaction when effectively implemented. The study identified key barriers, including inadequate funding, bureaucratic hurdles, and unclear policy directives that undermine QA effectiveness, leading to diminished teacher morale and suboptimal student outcomes. These findings offer valuable insights for the current study, where similar IQA guidelines are operationalized, highlighting the need to empirically examine their specific influence on

instructional effectiveness in public secondary schools in the Morogoro region, Tanzania. Furthermore, Stanley and Mhagama (2022) investigated the effectiveness of IQA practices in supporting quality education delivery within public secondary schools in Nyamagana District, Mwanza, Tanzania, employing a mixed-methods approach with convergent design to gather data from school heads, teachers, and district education officers through questionnaires, interviews, and document analysis. Their findings revealed that while IQA strategies such as routine lesson inspection, curriculum monitoring, and teacher performance evaluations demonstrated potential to strengthen pedagogical processes, their impact remained constrained by persistent challenges, including inadequate training for quality assurers, resource shortages, and resistance from overworked teaching staff, resulting in inconsistent implementation and limited improvement in classroom practices. Stanley and Mhagama's (2022) work underscore the contextual realities of the Tanzanian education system, providing a foundational reference for the current study in the Morogoro region, where similar IQA guidelines are applied, yet their specific influence on teachers' instructional effectiveness requires further empirical enquiry to identify region-specific adaptation strategies and enhance practical outcomes. In the same vein, Mtitu et al. (2023) explored the lived experiences of secondary academic staff serving as internal quality assurers in the Njombe region, Tanzania. The findings revealed that teachers' conception of IQA was shaped by the 2017 policy reform, which shifted from external oversight to school-based mechanisms. The findings indicated fragmented understanding among staff, with strengths in monitoring teaching practices, compounded by inadequate training and resource constraints that hindered effective execution. These contextual insights from Njombe underscore the relevance of the current Morogoro study, which extends the qualitative foundation by assessing IQA influence on teachers' instructional effectiveness, addressing methodological limitations through mixed-methods validation in comparable Tanzania public secondary schools.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Philosophy

The study adopted the pragmatist research philosophy, which emphasizes that the value of knowledge lies in its utility and ability to solve problems rather than adhering to fixed ideologies. It emphasizes practical outcomes and real-world applications.

3.2 Approach and Design

The study employed a convergent mixed-methods research design, combining quantitative and qualitative data to allow a better understanding of the research problem. By collecting data in a structured and organised manner, the study reduced bias and ensured the reliability and validity of the study findings.

3.3 Targeted Population

The population of the study was 2,652, consisting of 2,250 teachers from 250 public secondary schools, 125 school internal quality assurance team members, 09 CDQAOs, and 09 DSEOs from 09 Districts of the Morogoro Region, Tanzania.

3.3.1 Sample size and Sampling techniques

The sample size of the study consisted of 371 respondents, comprising 225 teachers, sampled using proportional simple random sampling from 250 public secondary schools. The 10% - 30% criterion of the targeted population was used for the big population (teachers) to obtain representations and reliability of the findings (Bullen, 2021). The study sampled 100 ISQATs using homogenous purposive sampling; the 25 other members were involved in the pilot study. The technique was preferred because where a group has a similar understanding of the topic, it is acceptable to include 4-8 members in the FGDs to express the ideas clearly without unnecessary noise (Lichtman, 2023). The 7 CDQAOs and 7 DSEOs were obtained using expert sampling as the head of monitoring and evaluation of IQA educational practices to ensure compliance with the set standards and regulations (URT, 2023). It should be noted that the remaining 02 officers in 02 district were involved in the pilot study; hence, they were excluded from the main investigation.

Table 1: The Summary of the Sampling Matrix

<i>SN</i>	Categories	Targeted Population	Sample Size
1.	District	09	07
2.	Schools	250	25
3.	Teachers	2,250	225
4.	School Interna Quality Assurance Teams	125	100
6.	CDQAOs	09	07
7	DSEOs	09	07
TOTAL		2652	371

Source: Researcher (2025)

3.4 Data Collection Instrument

The Questionnaire instrument was administered to teachers for data collection. Two experts from the education department at Jordan University College and one Quality Assurance expert validated the study tools. The reliability of the study tools was established using Cronbach's coefficient technique to calculate the dependability of the pilot results, yielding a grand mean reliability coefficient of 0.904. Qualitative data were collected through structured interviews with CDQAOs, while focus group discussions were conducted with ISQATs.

3.5 Data Analysis

Data were analyzed quantitatively and qualitatively. Quantitative data were descriptively analyzed in SPSS version 20, as well as thematic analysis procedures for qualitative data

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 2: Teachers’ responses on how IQA guidelines enhance teachers’ instructional effectiveness in Public Secondary Schools (n=201)

<i>S/N</i>	Statement	Responses (F & %)									
		SD		D		N		A		SA	
		<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>
1.	My school has internal quality assurance guidelines communicated to all teaching staff	24	11.9	41	20.4	02	1.0	83	41.2	51	25.3
2.	My school have the internal quality assurance team dedicated on overseeing teaching and learning practices	35	17.4	43	21.3	03	1.5	78	38.8	47	23.4
3.	The internal quality assurance guidelines have defining benchmarks and standards that I must meet in teaching and learning activities.	24	11.9	37	18.4	04	2.0	95	47.2	41	20.3

4. Ethical Consideration

The researcher obtained a research permit letter from both JUCo, the REO, and the MoEST before beginning data collection. In the field, the researcher obtains consent from the participants while safeguarding the privacy of study participants by deleting their identities. In the questionnaire, the researcher employed anonymity so that individuals and schools would not display their names. Schools were noted by numbers rather than by their full names. In data analysis, codes and numbers were employed. The researcher recognizes every information source to prevent academic plagiarism, which is defined as failing to correctly credit, quote, or acknowledge the words or ideas of another person (Okendo et al., 2020). Additionally, the researcher followed APA guidelines by citing study data using the 7th edition of the APA manual. When citing books, journal articles, tables, figures, quotes, and other significant elements in the manuscript.

4.	The guideline shows structured collaborative feedback sessions with my staff members to share innovative teaching strategies.	30	14.9	44	21.9	03	1.5	87	43.2	37	18.4
5.	The guideline aligns my teaching with clear objectives in each topic of the subject I teach to make my teaching workload manageable.	45	22.3	47	23.4	07	3.5	58	28.8	44	21.9
6.	The guideline lightens my assessment burden by identifying co-assessment activities under the school's internal quality assurance team.	42	20.9	74	36.8	02	1.0	40	20.0	43	21.3
7.	The guideline integrates online digital tools, such as online grade submission, to oversee teaching and learning progress.	66	32.8	52	25.8	0	0	45	22.4	38	18.9

Source: Field Data, (2025) **Key:** Strongly Disagree (SD), Disagree (D), Neutral (N), Agree (A), Strongly Agree (SA)

5.1 The Presence of IQA Guidelines Communicated to Teaching staff

From Table 2, the data indicate 66.5% of the respondents agree that their school has IQA guidelines communicated to all staff, contrasted by 32.3% disagreement. The findings signal a dominant yet imperfect alignment in policy dissemination that shapes instructional effectiveness through TQM principles of continuous improvement and stakeholders' involvement. This majority endorsement implies robust institutional commitment to TQM's systemic processes, though a notable dissent indicates gaps in equitable access and clarity which undermine instructional consistency and innovation as teachers grapple with uneven guidelines internalization. Qualitative data from Focus group discussion with SIQATs deepened the understanding. Members noted that although guidelines exist at policy level, their inconsistent communication and insufficient training limited teachers' awareness and practical application within schools. One FGD participant stated,

“We share the guidelines by regularly engage in discussion to establish uniformity in the implementation of the directives we receive, but we lack practical examples for classroom use” (FGDs G, April, 2025).

A similar response on IQA implementation was also expressed by FGDs T in which one SIQAT member said that,

“Our responsibilities were communicated to us by the headmaster, and those are the tasks we carry out, we were not provided with formal guidelines” (FGDs H, May, 2025).

The findings demonstrate a systemic communication gap that blocks effective knowledge transmission and internal dynamics, insufficient communication channels, and capacity building constraints hindering IQA practices which consequently affects teachers' perception of school support. These qualitative insights are supported by Fungilwa (2021) observation in Njombe who asserted that professional development significantly enhance teachers' autonomy and decision-making, yet there is inconsistent training due to resource shortages and poor-follow-up, this mirror 32.3% dissent and contradicting TQM principles.

5.2 The presence of SIQATs to oversee Teaching and Learning Practices

The statistics in Table 2 indicate 62.2% of teachers' respondents agree that their schools have IQA teams dedicated for overseeing teaching and learning practices in Morogoro region, contrasting with 38.7% disagreement. The findings indicate that while most perceived structural commitment, a substantial minority experiences oversight gaps that undermine instructional effectiveness through inconsistent monitoring loops which signalize a partial integration of TQM principles. The quantitative

divergence aligns closely with qualitative insights from the FGDs with the SIQATs, where one member noted,

“We crosscheck lesson plan preparation weekly, though we have limited time we only ensure that the intended period to be taught by teachers per week are fulfilled and then we write the report to the school heads” (FGD K Discussion, May, 2025).

Similarly, the DSEO interview remarked,

“In some schools with a good number of teachers, IQA team conduct better lesson delivery among teachers, but some of schools in our district have small limited number of teachers where even to formulate the IQA team becomes challenging” (DSEO E interview, May, 2025)

These findings are supported by Kitosi (2021) study who found that IQA strategies improve teaching and learning environment yet faltered amid overcrowded classrooms and shortage of teachers in community secondary schools in Kahama which contradict the national education policy for prioritizing SIQATs formation over capacity building, and inadequate teaching staff, indicating a need for targeted TQM intervention such as training to ensure instructional gains in public secondary schools in Morogoro region.

5.3 Defining Teaching Benchmarks and Standards

The survey results in Table 2 indicate a substantial majority 67.5% of teachers' respondents in public secondary schools of Morogoro region, Tanzania affirm the existence of IQA guidelines defining clear benchmarks and standards for teaching and learning activities, with 30.3% disagreeing and 02% neutral. The findings indicate a predominant perception of structured quality frameworks despite pockets of skepticism rooted in inconsistent enforcement and resource gaps. The distribution implies a moderate institutional readiness to guide instructional effectiveness but signals gaps in universal adoption that undermine TQM theory's emphasis on continuous improvement through customer-focused process (students are primary

beneficiaries in the education context) and evidence-based benchmarking to elevate teachers' effectiveness. This is corroborated by the FGDs with SIQATs, where one member notified,

“We have drafted guidelines which direct how a lesson plan should be prepared and how to conduct student assessments. This proves instrumental because teachers bear responsibility for preparing their lesson effectively, knowing that they will be inspected at the end of every week, but implementation varies due to teachers' workload” (FGD H Discussion, May, 2025).

Another member insisted on the lack of training among SIQATs on effective implementation of IQA at the school level, noting that the guidelines exist on paper but the team is sometimes struggling to meet head of school directives, as one member noted.

“We were simply assigned duties by the school head and instructed that it is our responsibility to ensure that the assigned tasks are implemented. It feels like we are performing all the activities of external quality assurers without being given any training” (FGD J Discussion, May, 2025).

Similarly, in interview with the district secondary education officer one officer stated,

Our schools in the district possess guidelines aligned with the ministry of education directives, the challenge lies in their implementation stemming from teachers' shortages. It is difficult for the school heads to assign internal quality assurance duties alongside other responsibilities. (DSEO E interview, May, 2025)

From these findings, the distribution indicate that while TQM theory emphasize on fostering accountability to enhance instructional effectiveness through defined standards as evidenced by improved lesson delivery in compliant schools, it occur unevenly because of contextual barriers like inadequate monitoring

which signify an important opportunity for targeted professional development to boost 67% majority towards full TQM integration, with expected outcomes of elevated student performance and school-wide excellence if gaps are bridged. As observed by Medard & Mwila (2022) in Temeke Municipality, who asserted the importance of IQA guidelines as critical components of the QA system, for providing clear expectations for teaching practices, curriculum implementation, and student assessment, which are essential in fostering a supportive teaching and learning environment.

5.4 Facilitate Structured Collaborative Feedback

Again, from Table 2, the combined percentage of teachers' respondents, 61.6% in the Morogoro region, agree that IQA guidelines support structured collaborative feedback sessions within staff, while 36.8% disagree. This suggests that IQA-informed feedback routines are partially institutionalized but remain unevenly perceived and experienced. The pattern implies that, for majority, the IQA framework is aligning with core tenets of TQM theory on teamwork, participative feedback, and evidence-based reflection on teachers' practices. This reveals a moderate significant endorsement of IQA guideline's role in fostering TQM principles of continuous improvement and employee involvement, implying that the guidelines provide a framework for peer learning and instructional enhancement, persistent implementation supports the information provided by FGD members who said;

"We collaboratively share effective teaching methodologies during MEWAKA sessions, and teachers who meticulously prepare lesson plans are empowered to guide their peers within the subject departments on how to design impactful lesson plans" (FGDs G, May, 2025).

The explanation aligned closely with the information provided by DCQAO, which said

"When we arrive at school, we normally emphasize the importance of teachers sharing effective teaching methods through MEWAKA sessions to enhance

the quality of teaching methods, and we urge heads of schools to closely monitor this process" (DCQAO G, interview, 05th May, 2025).

The findings are consistent with Kissa and Wandela (2022), who highlighted that positive relationships and cooperation between teachers and school quality assurance officers in Morogoro Municipality enhance pedagogical skills through feedback reports and collaboration. The structured nature of these sessions, as guided by IQA standards, ensures that feedback is systematic and actionable, contributing to professional growth and improved teaching practices (URT, 2023).

Yet the substantial minority of dissenting respondents signal that the implementation of these structured sessions is inconsistent, often superficial, and not fully understood as a collective process rather than a top-down inspection, which supports the evidence reporting that many SIQATs still focus narrowly on compliance checks rather than pedagogical dialogue (Makiya et al., 2023). The district education officer, however, acknowledged that the guidelines are there, but teachers do not always recognize their benefits because sometimes the staff meetings become long talks on other administrative issues without a clear focus on IQA objectives, as one officer noted.

"Some school leaders do not emphasize joint meetings for discussing collaborative teaching strategies; instead, they focus primarily on directives and instruction to teachers. This is a predominant challenge in many schools in our district" (DSEO E interview, May, 2025)

This reveals a structural gap between policy design and enactment, with implications for the TQM principle of systematic data-driven improvements. When feedback is not consistently operationalized as a cycle of observation, discussion, agreed-on actions, and subsequent review, the perceived value of IQA collapses for a significant proportion of teachers. Hence, 61.6% to 36.8% split reflects both a real but fragile commitment to collaborative quality cultures in

integrating TQM-oriented feedback as a routine, visible, and outcome-oriented process, thereby constraining the extent to which IQA guidelines translate into discernible gains in instructional effectiveness across public secondary schools in the Morogoro region.

5.5 Aligning Teaching with Clear Objectives

The statistics further shows 50.7% of the respondents agree, 45.7% disagree, while 3.5% remained neutral on the IQA guidelines aligning teaching with clear objectives in each subject topic, thereby making the workload manageable. The findings highlight a polarized perception of IQA guidelines' effectiveness in public secondary schools in Morogoro region, implying a partial success in applying TQM principles such as systematic processes and customer focus of aligning teaching and learners' needs, yet revealing significant gaps in workload reduction and instructional clarity that undermine teacher efficacy and overall instructional effectiveness.

The discussion with SIQATs further acknowledged that the guidelines help teachers to set their subject goals while critiquing the implementation realities among teachers. It was noted that teachers struggle with a heavy workload, as one member noted,

“We have guidelines, it is true, but there is no reality of implementing these guidelines because there are few teachers, for instance, you may find a mathematics teacher teaching two classes with almost six streams, the teaching workload is very heavy” (FGDs K, May, 2025).

These findings imply that while the IQA guidelines promote structured lesson objectives for some teachers, others view the guidelines as imposing bureaucratic burdens that cannot adapt to real classroom demands, such as class size and resource shortages in the Morogoro region, as observed by Kingu and Wandela (2022), which limit the TQM continuous improvement ethos. Another SIQAT leader, when asked about how IQA guidelines contribute to supportive teaching and learning, replied that the guidelines exist but require stronger enforcement to translate standards into observable instructional gains, as he noted,

“The guideline promotes teachers’ accountability as it provides a structured roadmap on lesson planning, assessment, and evaluation, but it requires training and enforcement because some teachers perceive it as a burden” (FGDs K, May, 2025).

Alongside, the quality assurance officer's observation insisted that although IQA guidelines are mandated, the enforcement is hindered by inadequate teaching staff and accountability. QA visits often revealed gaps between the IQA framework and classroom realities, as one officer said,

“Our role is to ensure schools comply with QA standards; however, the physical infrastructure of many schools in our district is not conducive to effective teaching and learning, characterized by an inadequate teacher-student ratio” (DCQAO 5 interview, April 2025).

These findings resonate with the analyses by Fungilwa (2021) on quality assurance within the public secondary schools' educational system in Tanzania, emphasizing that for successful instructional outcomes, there needs to be a considerable focus on IQA implementation, infrastructure, and adaptability.

In line to that, the 3.5% neutral responses suggest that not all teachers fully experience the importance of IQA guidelines in managing workload, due to contextual factors such as inadequate training on implementing IQA practices and resource shortages, the findings is consistent with Mpunda (2023) study in Iringa, who observed that shortages of teaching and learning materials undermine the effectiveness of IQA measures, as teachers struggle to translate objectives into practice without adequate resources.

Overall, these findings have brought about a well-defined scenario that calls for an emphasis on improved operational implementation and adaptability within the IQA framework. The findings call for context-tailored enhancements to turn guidelines into true workload managers, fostering teacher instructional effectiveness.

5.6 Lighten Assessment through Co-Assessment

Furthermore, the data in Table 2 indicate a high proportion of respondents 57.7% disagreeing that IQA guidelines lighten their assessment burden, against only 41.3% who agree. This suggests that in practice, the guidelines-based co-assessment activities of the School Internal Quality Assurance Teams are not yet functioning as a true shared responsibility mechanism under TQM. This pattern indicates that, instead of creating a systematic school-wide effort to distribute assessment tasks, the guidelines are perceived more as an additional layer of formal duties that teachers must still carry largely on their own. The FGDs with SIQATs cemented this finding, where one member elaborated,

“Teachers sometimes perceive collaboration as conflict due to differences in work approaches, arguing that one teacher cooperating with another is often seen as coercion, which leads to conflicts among teachers.” (FGD J, May 2025).

Another member insisted,

“In our school, most teachers still think that IQA is about checking their lesson plan, not about working together on assessment, moderation, and feedback (FGD J, May 2025).”

The narrative underscores a persistent perception of IQA as a surveillance rather than collegial support, while another added,

“The guidelines tell us what to do, without showing clearly how we should divide assessment work between subjects’ teachers and SIQATs” (FGD L, May 2025).

Highlighting procedural ambiguity and implementation gaps.

In line with TQM theory, which stresses continuous improvement through teamwork and process optimization, the findings imply structural weaknesses characterized by unclear role division between teachers and the SIQATs, poor task standardization, and limited capacity of the team to participate in feedback activities. The findings imply that IQA guidelines in public

secondary schools in Morogoro region have been adopted more in a structural form than of process re-engineering; instead of mapping and redesigning the assessment process to remove duplication, standardized tools and formalize co-assessment such as through joint test construction, collaborative marking and collective analysis of results, the system has largely overlaid existing practices with additional record-keeping and compliance checks, thereby failing to deliver the expected reduction in individual teacher burden. This is consistent with the study in Arusha, Tanzania, which identified poor understanding of IQA, where the SIQATs often focus more on monitoring record attendance practices in the classroom than on supporting core instructional tasks such as assessment and feedback (Makiya et al., 2023).

The statistically visible minority 41.3% who agree that the guidelines lighten their assessment burden, indicate that they are at schools where the SIQATs are more mature and operate in line with TQM principles, using guidelines to coordinate common examinations, share marking among subject panels, moderate assessment instruments, and use data for school-wide improvement, thus demonstrating the latent potential of IQA to enhance instructional effectiveness when enacted as a collaborative quality system rather than a top-down control mechanism. The overall mixed but predominantly negative perception implies a partial and uneven translation of TQM-inspired IQA guidelines into practice; the guidelines have not yet been internalized as a tool for co-assessment and collective responsibility for quality, and unless capacity building, participatory implementation, and process-focused redesign prioritized, IQA guidelines is unlikely to function as genuine TQM mechanism that lightens assessment burden and support teachers instructional effectiveness in public secondary schools in, Morogoro region.

5.7 Integrating Digital Tools for Progress Oversight

The statistics in Table 2 indicate that 58.6% of the respondents disagree, while 41.3% agree that the IQA guidelines integrate online digital tools, such as online grade submission systems, to oversee teaching and learning progress, which signals a

structural misalignment framework and its technological operationalization in public secondary schools in the Morogoro region. From a TQM theory perspective, which emphasizes continuous improvement, data-driven decision making, and stakeholders' responsiveness, this split indicates that the current IQA guidelines remain largely administratively oriented and paper-based, failing to fully harness information systems as mechanisms for real-time feedback, process optimization, and instructional level accountability. The FGDs with the SIQATs revealed that, despite recognition of digital tools' potential, implementation is hampered by weak infrastructural support and limited instructional capacity, one team member remarked,

“We know that online platforms can help us track learners' performance faster, but in our district, the internet is slow, the electricity is unreliable, but most of all, most teachers are not even aware of how to use computers, and as a team, we have not been trained on how to use this system within our IQA routines.” (FGDs P, May 2025)

Similarly, in an interview with the DSEO, the DSEO highlighted technological gaps at the systemic level: the DSEO observed,

“The policy says on modernizing the education system, but at the school-level, heads of schools and subject departments largely are still managing examination records and lesson monitoring manually” (DSEO B, interview, May 2025).

While the QA officer noted,

“... we indeed inspect registers and handwritten reports; if the guidelines integrate online grade submission as it is for the national examinations results, we would be able to see trends in learner performance and adjust supervision strategies immediately and in time” (CDQAO D, interview, May 2025).

The qualitative narratives corroborate the quantitative skew toward disagreement, suggesting that most teachers perceive the IQA guidelines as technologically inert and

disconnected from the data-rich reality of modern teaching, thereby constraining their ability to refine instruction based on timely, granular evidence. This stands in relative tension with broader empirical work on technology integration in education, which shows that teachers generally hold positive perceptions of digital tools and that their use can enhance instructional effectiveness when accompanied by adequate infrastructure, training, and supportive policies according to Asumah and Antwi (2024), yet these benefits are contingent on systemic readiness and professional development which the current IQA guidelines in Morogoro region appears to under-provide. Consequently, the divergence between the majority of teachers who disagree and the minority who agree about digital integration reflects a technological deficit and a quality management paradox. The findings call immediate intervention on technological integration for creating a sustainable and equitable education system that fosters instructional effectiveness across public secondary schools.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Conclusion

The findings of this study demonstrates that effective and structured IQA guidelines serve as an instrument of accountability and a catalyst for reflective teaching and sustained instructional improvements. Accordingly, the study underscores the critical role of consistent institutional support, capacity building, and leadership commitment in integrating IQA guidelines that enhance teaching performance. The findings contribute to the growing discourse on educational management by illustrating that the IQA when contextually adapted and collaboratively executed, forms a pivotal foundation for achieving sustainable instructional excellence within public secondary schools.

6.2 Recommendations

In light of the study findings, it is recommended that the Ministry of Education, Science, and Technology (MoEST) strengthen institutional framework guiding IQA in public secondary

schools by ensuring that quality assurance standards are contextually responsive and evidence-based. Educational authorities at regional and district level should institutionalize continuous professional development programs aligned with IQA benchmarks to enhance teachers' pedagogical competence, instructional planning, and reflective practice. Moreover, the establishment of collaborative monitoring system involving heads of schools, quality assurance officers, and teachers is crucial for fostering transparency, accountability, and shared responsibility in maintaining instructional quality.

The study also recommends that the IQA guidelines be integrated into school improvement plans with clear performance indicators and feedback mechanisms that support data-driven instructional decisions. Future research may expand on this work by examining how digital technologies strategies can be integrated into IQA guidelines to sustain instructional effectiveness and promote a culture of continuous improvement across schools in the Morogoro region, Tanzania.

7. DISCLAIMER (ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE)

Authors(s) hereby declare that ChatGPT, generative AI technology, has been used during writing for editing and refining language to enhance clarity and coherence. The conceptualization, research, and core content of this article are the original work of the author

8. REFERENCES

Ali, A. I., & Hermansyah, E. (2024). Quality Assurance System Policy in Education: A Comparative Study Between Indonesia and Finland. *Jurnal Penelitian Kebijakan Pendidikan*, 17(1).

Arslan, M. (2025). Quality and quality assurance in teacher professional development: A comparative study. *Journal of Innovative Research in Teacher Education*, 6(2).

Asuamah Yeboah, S., & Antwi Boasiako, A. (2024). Beyond the Classroom: Quality Assurance in Developing Nations.

Camilleri, M. A., & Camilleri, A. C. (2020). The Sustainable Development Goal on quality education. *The Future of the UN Sustainable Development Goals: Business Perspectives for Global Development in 2030*, 261-277

Council, M. D., & Plan, S. (2017, February). The United Republic of Tanzania President's Office, Regional Administration and Local Government.

Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2023). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches* (6th ed.) SAGE

ESCAP, (2019). *SDG 4: Quality education: ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all*.

Falah, F., Zohriah, A., & Firdaus, R. (2025). The Concept of Total Quality Management in Managing Educational Institutions. *al-Afkar, Journal for Islamic Studies*, 8(2), 1286-1294.

Fungilwa, A. C. (2021). Effectiveness of Internal School Quality Assurance in Teaching and Learning Among Public Secondary Schools in Tanzania, a Case of Njombe Town Council (Master's thesis, University of Dodoma (Tanzania)).

Idris, O. O. (2023). Quality assurance and teachers' productivity in public secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. *Journal Of Capital Development in Behavioural Sciences*, 11(2), 58-72.

Jester, P. (2024). Total Quality Management: Paving the Road to Excellence. *Quality*, 63(12), 15-15.

Kauko, J., Pitkänen, H., & Varjo, J. (2022). Quality in Finnish Comprehensive Schools. Successful public policy in the Nordic countries: Cases, lessons, challenges.

Kingu, N. E., & Wandela, E. L. (2022). Assessment of the school quality assurance lesson observation tool in enhancing an active pedagogical paradigm in Tanzania secondary schools. *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, 32(4), 42-51.

Kissa, C. M., & Wandela, E. L. (2022). Secondary School Teachers' Perceptions on Quality Assurance's Feedback Reports for Effective Teaching in Morogoro Municipality, Tanzania. *American Journal of Education and Information Technology*, 6(2), 66-80.

Kitosi, F. G. (2021). Assessment of the Implementation of Internal Quality Assurance in

Public Community Secondary Schools in Tanzania (Doctoral dissertation, The Open University of Tanzania).

Makiya, R., Mnyanyi, C., & Ngirwa, C. (2023). Examining School Quality Assurance Criteria for Enhancing Learning Achievements in Public Primary Schools in Arusha Region, Tanzania. *Asian Research Journal of Arts & Social Sciences*, 20(2), 1-13.

Mapunda, E. O. (2023). The Effects of School Quality Assurance on Teachers' Performance in Public Primary Schools in Iringa District, Tanzania. *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, 49(1), 118-124.

Medard, G., & Mwila, P. M. (2022). School Quality Assurance Guidelines: Their Implementation and Challenges in Public Secondary Schools in Temeke Municipality, Tanzania. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 6(10), 124-133.

Mtiti, E. C., Makwinya, N. M., Ishemo, R. P., & Msangya, B. W. (2023). Internal Quality Assurers' Conception on Internal Quality Assurance (IQA) process: Examining Lived Experience of Secondary School Academic Member of staff within Njombe Region, Tanzania. *International Journal of Research in Social Science and Humanities (IJRSS)* ISSN: 2582-6220, DOI: 10.47505/IJRSS, 4(7), 36-45.

Mutemi, D. T., & Mwila, P. M. (2025). School Quality Assurance Feedback: Its Role in Promoting the Teaching Process in Public Secondary Schools in Temeke Municipality, Tanzania. *Action Research Journal Indonesia (ARJI)*, 7(2), 309-329.

Ng'hoboko, L. D. (2024). The Contributions of Internal School Quality Assurance on Enhancing Teaching and Learning Process in Public Primary Schools in Tanzania (Doctoral dissertation, The Open University of Tanzania).

Özkan, E., & Şahin, Y. (2025). Policy, Governance, and Quality Assurance in Education Systems: Comparative and Empirical Perspectives. *VFAST Transactions on Education and Social Sciences*, 13(4), 01-25.

Phumphongkhasorn, P., Damnoen, S., Tuwanno, P. D. M., Srichan, P. W., & Udomdhammaree, P. (2022). Educational quality assurance and school management standards according to international. *Asia Pacific Journal of Religions and Cultures*, 6(1), 1-16.

Quansah, M. A. (2022). Factors affecting the effectiveness of the internal audit function in public and private universities in Ghana (Doctoral dissertation, University of Education, Winneba).

Stanley, A., & Mhagama, M. (2022). Assessment of the effectiveness of internal quality assurance in the provision of quality education in public secondary schools in Nyamagana District, Mwanza Region. *Research and Analysis Journal*, 5(11), 01-10.

Suyanto, S., & Ulfah, Y. F. (2024). Enhancing Education Quality through Internal Quality Assurance Strategies. *Profetika: Jurnal Studi Islam*, 25(01), 107-118

URT (2017) School Quality Assurance Handbook, Dar es Salaam, Tanzania, Ministry of Education, Science and Technology.

URT (2019). School quality assurance. Dodoma: MoEST. www.unesco.org

URT (2023). School quality assurance. Dodoma: MoEST. www.unesco.org

Yoon, I., & Goddard, R. D. (2023). Professional development quality and instructional effectiveness: Testing the mediating role of teacher self-efficacy beliefs. *Professional Development in Education*, 1-15.